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Corresponding Author: Professor Robert R. Gamache, PhD

Corresponding Author's Institution: Univ. of Mass. Lowell

First Author: Anne Laraia, undergraduate

Order of Authors: Anne Laraia, undergraduate; Robert R Gamache, PhD; Jean-Michel Hartmann, PhD; Agnes Perrin, PhD; Laura Gomez, PhD

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**Department of Environmental,
Earth, and Atmospheric Sciences**
*University of Massachusetts Lowell
One University Avenue
Lowell, MA 01854*

Dr. Laurence Rothman
Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer
Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics
Atomic and Molecular Physics Division, MS50
60 Garden Street
Cambridge MA 02138-1516

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Dear Larry,

I have submitted electronically the manuscript entitled “Theoretical Calculations of N₂-broadened Half-Widths of ν_5 Transitions of HNO₃” by A. Laraia, R. R. Gamache, J.-M. Hartmann, A. Perrin, L. Gomez. We submit this manuscript for publication in the HITRAN special edition of the Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer.

Sincerely,

Professor Robert R. Gamache

Robert_Gamache@uml.edu

Theoretical Calculations of N₂-broadened Half-Widths of ν_5 Transitions of HNO₃A. Laraia⁽¹⁾, R. R. Gamache^{(1)*}, J.-M. Hartmann⁽²⁾, A. Perrin⁽²⁾, L. Gomez⁽²⁾

(1) University of Massachusetts Lowell and University of Massachusetts, School of Marine Sciences, Department of Environmental, Earth, and Atmospheric Sciences, 265 Riverside Street, University of Massachusetts Lowell, Lowell, MA 01854-5045, Lowell, MA USA

(2) Laboratoire Interuniversitaire des Systèmes Atmosphériques (LISA), CNRS UMR 7584) CNRS and Universities Paris 12 and Paris 7, 61 Av. Général de Gaulle, 94010 Créteil Cedex, France

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Abstract:

A number of satellite instruments are measuring nitric acid, HNO₃, in the Earth's atmosphere. In order to do retrievals of temperature and concentration profiles, the spectral parameters for many thousands of HNO₃ transitions must be known. Currently the HITRAN database uses a constant estimated value for the air-broadened half-width of HNO₃. To help improve the line shape parameters, complex Robert-Bonamy calculations were made to determine N₂-broadened half-widths and line shifts for some 5000 transitions of HNO₃ in the ν_5 band. The intermolecular potential is a sum of electrostatic terms (dipole-quadrupole and quadrupole-quadrupole), isotropic induction and London dispersion terms, and the atom-atom potential expanded to eighth order. The trajectory parameters were adjusted to yield better agreement with measurement. Velocity integrated calculations were made at seven temperatures in order to determine the temperature dependence of the half-widths. The half-width data are compared with available measurements. The average percent difference between the measured and

¹ * Corresponding author : (978) 934-3904, Robert_Gamache@uml.edu

calculated half-widths is -2.5. The temperature, vibrational, and rotational state dependence of the half-width are investigated.

Keywords

Complex Robert Bonamy formalism, half-width, HNO_3 , N_2 -broadening, temperature dependence of half-width, vibrational and rotational state dependence

1.0 Introduction

Nitric acid, HNO_3 , is an important minor constituent in the Earth's atmosphere. It is the main stratospheric reservoir species of the NO_x family. Photolysis of gas phase HNO_3 releases NO_2 , enabling a major pathway for the deactivation of chlorine via the reformation of ClONO_2 from NO_2 and ClO . The polar stratospheric clouds (PSCs) that form in the very low temperatures of polar winter remove HNO_3 , a key component of PSCs, from the gas phase. PSC particles provide surfaces on which heterogeneous chemical reactions occur that convert chlorine from its reservoir species (e.g., ClONO_2 , HCl) to the highly reactive forms (e.g., ClO) that participate in the catalytic cycles of ozone destruction. If PSC particles grow large enough they can settle out of the lower stratosphere carrying the HNO_3 with them in a process known as denitrification. When denitrification is severe the formation of ClONO_2 is limited, allowing enhanced ClO and thus chemical ozone destruction to persist. Thus HNO_3 has a major role in both the activation and the deactivation of chlorine and indirectly affects the extent, duration, and cumulative magnitude of stratospheric ozone depletion [1-3].

As a result of the importance of nitric acid's role in the major catalytic cycles for stratospheric ozone loss [4, 5] a number of balloon, aircraft, and satellite instruments are retrieving the concentration profiles of HNO₃. In the Polar Aura Validation Experiment (PAVE) Coffey *et al.* [6] flew the NCAR FTS onboard a NASA DC-8 aircraft to measure a number of constituents, including HNO₃ in the 867.50-871.80 cm⁻¹ region, and make comparisons with measurements from the Microwave Limb Sounder (MLS) [7], High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS) [8] and Tropospheric Emission Spectrometer (TES) [9] experiments aboard the Aura satellite. Kinnison *et al.* [10] report on global observations of HNO₃ made using channels 7, 8, and 9 of the HIRDLS instrument. Santee *et al.* [11], in a validation of the AURA MLD HNO₃ measurements, compare the data from the MLS 190 and 240 GHz radiometers with data from the balloon measurements; JPL MkIV solar occultation Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometer [12], the Smithsonian Astrophysical Observatory (SAO) far-infrared spectrometer (FIRS-2) [13], and the JPL Submillimeterwave Limb Sounder-2 (SLS-2) [14], with data from aircraft; PAVE, the University of New Hampshire (UNH) Soluble Acidic Gases and Aerosols (SAGA) instrument [15], with the NOAA chemical ionization mass spectrometer (CIMS) [16], and other satellite measurements. The Michelson Interferometer for Passive Atmospheric Sounding (MIPAS) on the European Space Agency (ESA) Environmental Satellite (Envisat) is a high-resolution infrared limb-sounding Fourier-transform spectrometer, which is measuring HNO₃ in the spectral region near 870 cm⁻¹ [17, 18]. The Swedish-led Odin satellite has the Submillimetre Radiometer (SMR) which observes limb thermal emission from HNO₃ on roughly two measurement days per week using an autocorrelator spectrometer centered at 544.6 GHz

[19]. The Improved Limb Atmospheric Spectrometer (ILAS) on board the Advanced Earth Observing Satellite (ADEOS) measured nitric acid profiles from November 1996 to June 1997 at high latitudes in both hemispheres [20]. The Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment Fourier Transform Spectrometer (ACE-FTS) on the Canadian Space Agency's SCISAT-1 mission measures high spectral resolution (0.02 cm^{-1}) solar occultation spectra over the range $750\text{--}4400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ [21]. The HNO_3 retrieval is based primarily on a set of microwindows covering the $1690\text{--}1730\text{ cm}^{-1}$ spectral range, with additional microwindows in the range $860\text{--}880\text{ cm}^{-1}$ used for measurements in the upper troposphere.

In a related study, Gomez *et al.* [22] have discussed the state of the spectroscopic parameters for HNO_3 for use in retrievals. The data available in the HITRAN [23] and GEISA [24] databases were improved in Ref. [25] in the 11.3 and $8.3\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ regions using new parameters for the line positions [26, 27], new line intensity data by Chackerian *et al.* [28], and a simple empirical model for the air-broadened half-widths [29] to replace the constant default value. While the residuals between atmospheric spectra recorded by MIPAS and those calculated using these new parameters are considerably reduced when compared with results obtained using the previous line parameters available in HITRAN or GEISA, there still are some significant features that can be observed in the residuals. The focus of the Gomez *et al.* paper was to further investigate nitric acid absorption in order to improve spectra calculations and correct for some of the observed discrepancies. This paper discusses the calculation of the N_2 -broadened half-widths that were used in the Gomez *et al.* paper to replace the simple empirical model.

Structure of the HNO_3 infrared spectrum:

In its equilibrium configuration, HNO₃ is a C_s- type planar molecule [30]. HNO₃ has 9 normal modes ν_i ($i=1,9$), ν_8 and ν_9 are of A'' symmetry, while the ν_1 to ν_7 modes are of A' symmetry. According to the selection rules for an electric dipole moment transition, vibrational bands involving an odd variation of $|\nu_8+\nu_9|$ are C-type bands, while bands with $\Delta|\nu_8+\nu_9|=\text{even}$ are hybrid-type bands (i.e. with both A-, and B-type transitions). However, the main cold bands appearing in the 11 μm , ν_5 and $2\nu_9$ located at 879.109 and 896.448 cm^{-1} , respectively, which are hybrid in principle, are mostly A-type bands. In order to understand the HNO₃ spectrum, one has to take into account some specific features:

- First, the relative intensities within each band. For HNO₃ A-type bands, the strongest lines involve $[J, K_a, K_c]$ rotational levels with $K_c \sim J$ in the P- and R- branches while for Q- branches only lines with $K_a \sim J$ are actually observable.

- Second, a clustering of rotational levels involving the same J and the same values of K_a or K_c . Indeed, because of the particular values of the rotational constants: nitric acid is an oblate molecule with $A \sim B \sim 2C$ ($A \sim 0.43\text{cm}^{-1}$, $B \sim 0.41\text{cm}^{-1}$ and $C \sim 0.20\text{cm}^{-1}$ for the H¹⁴N¹⁶O₃ isotopic species) two types of clustering of states occur which correspond to:

- (i) either to the $[J, K_a=J-K_c, K_c]$ and $[J, K_a=J-K_c+1, K_c]$ rotational levels for $J \geq 10$ and $K_a \leq J/2$,

- (ii) or to the $[J, K_a, K_c=J-K_a]$ and $[J, K_a, K_c=J-K_a+1]$ rotational levels for $J \geq 15$ and $K_a \geq J-2$. In this case K_a may be considered as a "good" quantum number.

Actually the two levels involved in the first type of clustering belong to the same symmetry species in C_s because they involve the same K_c value and the two levels

involved in the second type of clustering belong to different symmetry species in C_s because they involve different K_c values.

The effects of these degeneracies on the half-widths and their temperature dependence are discussed below.

2.0 Complex Robert-Bonamy Formalism applied to the HNO₃-N₂ system

The calculations are made using the complex implementation of the Robert-Bonamy theory [31] (CRB). Here the method is summarized, details of the method can be found in Refs. [32-34]. The calculations are complex valued and yield the pressure-broadened half-width and pressure-induced line shift from a single calculation. Within the CRB formalism the half-width, γ , and line shift, δ , of a ro-vibrational transition $f \leftarrow i$ are given by minus the imaginary part and the real part, respectively, of the diagonal elements of the complex relaxation matrix. In computational form the half-width and line shift are usually expressed in terms of the Liouville scattering matrix [35, 36]

$$(\gamma - i\delta) = \frac{n_2}{2 \pi c} \left\langle v \left[1 - e^{-R S_2(f,i,J_2,v,b)} e^{-i I S_2(f,i,J_2,v,b)} \right] \right\rangle_{v,b,J_2} \quad (1)$$

where n_2 is the number density of perturbers and $\langle \rangle_{v,b,J_2}$ represents an average over all trajectories (impact parameter b and initial relative velocity v) and initial rotational state J_2 of the collision partner. $S_2 = {}^R S_2 + i I S_2$ is the second order terms in the expansion of the scattering matrix, which depends on the ro-vibrational states involved and associated

collision induced jumps from these levels, on the intermolecular potential and characteristics of the collision dynamics. Note, Eq. (1) generally contains the vibrational dephasing term, S_1 , which arises only for transitions where there is a change in the vibrational state. The potential leading to S_1 is written in terms of the isotropic induction and London dispersion interactions which depend on the vibrational dependence of the dipole moment and polarizability of the radiating molecule. These parameters are not available for HNO_3 and the S_1 term has been omitted from the calculation. Note, the effect of the S_1 term on the half-width often tends to be small. The exact form of the S_2 term is given in Refs. [32-34].

The intermolecular potential used in the calculations is comprised of an electrostatic component (dipole and quadrupole moments of HNO_3 with the quadrupole moment of N_2) and an atom-atom component. The heteronuclear Lennard-Jones parameters for the atomic pairs are determined using the "combination rules" of Hirschfelder et al. [37]. The atom-atom distance, r_{ij} is expressed in terms of the center of mass separation, R , via the expansion in $1/R$ of Sack [38]. Here the formulation of Neshyba and Gamache [39] expanded to eighth order is used. The dynamics of the collision process are based on Robert and Bonamy's second order in time approximation to the true trajectories [31], which gives curved rather than straight line trajectories. These trajectories are based on the isotropic part of the intermolecular potential.

The wavefunctions used to evaluate the reduced matrix elements are obtained by diagonalizing the Watson Hamiltonian [40] in a symmetric top basis. The wavefunctions for the ground vibrational state are determined using the Watson-Hamiltonian constants

of Goldman *et al.* [41] and those for the ν_5 vibrational state use the Watson constants of Maki and Wells [42]. The molecular constants for N_2 are from Huber and Herzberg [43].

The molecular parameters for the HNO_3-N_2 system used in this work are as follows: The dipole moment takes the lower limit from the work of Cox and Riveros [44], [45] $\mu=2.15$ D. The quadrupole moments are from Albinus *et al.* [46] taken with HNO_3 in the I^R representation: $Q_{xx}=-3.34\pm 0.23 \cdot 10^{-26}$ esu, $Q_{yy}=+1.06\pm 0.33 \cdot 10^{-26}$ esu, $Q_{zz}=+2.28\pm 0.23 \cdot 10^{-26}$ esu. The quadrupole moment of nitrogen is from Mulder *et al.* [45], $Q_{zz}=-1.4\pm 0.1 \cdot 10^{-26}$ esu. The atom-atom parameters were obtained using the standard combination rules with the atom-atom parameters for homonuclear diatomics determined by Bouanich [47] by fitting to second virial coefficient data. These parameters are reported in Table 1. In the calculations, the atom-atom potential is expanded to eight-order in the molecular centers of mass separation.

In the parabolic trajectory approximation the isotropic part of the interaction potential is taken into account in determining the distance, effective velocity, and force at closest approach. To simplify the trajectory calculations the isotropic part of the atom-atom expansion is fit to an isotropic Lennard-Jones 6-12 potential. In order to improve agreement with measurement, the trajectories were modified by adjusting the isotropic Lennard-Jones parameters such that the calculations would better agree with measurement. To accomplish this in a reasonable amount of time eight transitions were chosen from the measurements of Goyette *et al.* [48]. The results of this adjustment are given in Table 2.

3.0 Calculations

The selection of transitions in the ν_5 band to study was made in several stages. First ν_5 band transitions with an intensity greater or equal to $S_{\max}/100$ were taken from the HITRAN database [23], where S_{\max} is the maximum line intensity in the band. This produced a list of 15 609 transitions. The list was filtered removing all transitions with $J>45$; the resulting list contained 12 553 transitions. To shorten the list of transitions an intensity cutoff of $5. \times 10^{-22} \text{ cm}^{-1}/\text{molec cm}^{-2}$ was applied. This produced a list of 5011 transitions. However, due to limitations in the codes, calculations could not be made for a number of the high J (P- and R-branch) transitions resulting in a final list of 4979 transitions that were studied.

The calculation of the half-width and line shift were made for these transitions of HNO_3 broadened by N_2 at seven temperatures (200., 225., 275., 296., 300., 375., 500. K) by explicitly performing the averaging over the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution of velocities (Eq. (1)). The intermolecular potential for the calculations is described above. From the eight transitions studied in the optimization of the trajectory parameters, a sense of the magnitude of the line shifts in the rotation band can be obtained. The shifts were both positive and negative and the largest magnitude was $0.97 \times 10^{-3} \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ atm}^{-1}$. The calculations for the ν_5 band transitions did not use the S_1 part of the intermolecular potential, hence the resulting line shifts are not reported.

For applications to atmospheres, the temperature dependence of the half-widths must be known. Theoretical consideration of the temperature dependence of the half-width for a one term intermolecular potential gives the power law model [49],

$$\gamma(T) = \gamma(T_0) \left\{ \frac{T_0}{T} \right\}^n, \quad (2)$$

where n is called the temperature exponent.

The temperature exponent was determined for each transition by a least-squares fit of $\ln[\gamma(T)/\gamma(T_0)]$ vs. $\ln[T_0/T]$ using the seven temperatures of the study. The error in the temperature exponent was determined as follows: The temperature exponents were calculated using the half-width values at any two of the temperatures studied. With seven temperatures this yields twenty-one 2-point temperature exponents. The difference between each 2-point temperature exponent and the 7-point fit value is calculated. The error is taken as the largest of these differences. While this procedure tends to yield the maximum error in the temperature exponent, given the nature of the data and other uncertainties it is thought to be more reasonable than a statistical value taken from the fit.

4.0 Discussion

Half-width as a function of the rotational quantum numbers

The calculations were made for 4979 transitions in the ν_5 band with J'' ranging from 1 to 45 and K_c'' from 0 to 43. At 296 K the half-widths go from a minimum value of $0.0923 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ atm}^{-1}$ to a maximum value of $0.1316 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ atm}^{-1}$. The leading electrostatic component for this system is the dipole-quadrupole interaction. With the large dipole moment of HNO_3 , $\mu=2.15 \text{ D}$, large half-widths are expected. In Fig. 1 the half-width is plotted versus $J''+0.9*(K_c''/J'')$ where the plot symbols are K_c'' . The factor that is added on to J'' for the abscissa is to spread points out for a particular J'' value as a function

of K_c'' . The plot does show some structure. For example, the bottom line of points consists of transitions with $K_c''=0$ and 1. Above this, the series of lines are for $K_c''=1$ and 2, then $K_c''=2$ and 3, etc. After $K_c''=3$ the lines blend and for many of the transitions studied there is considerable overlap and any propensity rules are difficult to establish.

To try to better see the structure, plots were made of the N_2 -broadened half-width versus the lower rotational state *index* ($J''*(J''+1)+K_a''-K_c''+1$). The plots were made in panels for a given J'' of the index running from 1 to 2025 with the $|\Delta K_c|=1$ points plotted in blue, the $|\Delta K_c|=3$ plotted in red, and the $|\Delta K_c|>3$ plotted in aqua. The transitions occur in doublets and are dominated by $|\Delta K_c|=1$ transitions. What is observed is that for each value of J'' there is a sequence of points (Note, the sequence is for $K_c''=J''$ going to $K_c''=0$). At low J'' the points have roughly the same half-width for the whole sequence with a slight decrease where $K_c''=0$. By $J''=8$ the half-widths are decreasing noticeably as K_c'' goes to zero. At around $J''=18$ the data have a small decrease for high values of K_c'' followed by an increase in the half-widths as K_c'' decreases, then at $K_c''\sim 6$ there is a sharp decrease. The trend of the half-width with *index* becomes more evident for larger J'' values. To demonstrate this, the sequence for $J''=27$ is plotted in Fig. 2. This corresponds to the *index* running from 730 (27_{027}) to 784 (27_{270}). In the top panel the symbols are an asterisk (*) for the P-branch, open circle (O) for the Q-branch, and open delta (Δ) for the R-branch transitions. For K_c'' large the

half-widths for the R-branch transitions are the lowest. At $index=738$ and slightly larger the Q-branch half-widths lie between the R- and P-branch values. The half-width for the R-, Q-, and P-branch transitions steadily increase. At around $index=770$ the values start to spread but the general trend is for the half-widths to decrease rapidly beyond this point. Note, for $index > 770$ the P-branch lines have the smallest half-widths followed by Q- and R-branch transitions. To understand the how the structure varies with K_c'' the lower panel of Fig. 2 is the same data plotted where the plot symbol is K_c'' of the transition. Showing as the $index$ increases the values of K_c'' decrease.

Table 3 gives the data for the sequence of points for $index$ equal 1297 ($36_0 36_0$) to 1397 ($36_{36} 0$). The data have been sorted on the value of the half-width. The degeneracies discussed above for the line positions and line intensities occur also for the half-widths and their temperature dependence. Indeed, for these degenerate transitions identical values were achieved for the line width parameters (see Table 3).

Vibrational dependence of the half-width

Half-widths for $300 \nu_5$ transitions were compared with the computed half-width for the corresponding rotation band transitions to obtain some sense of the vibrational dependence of the half-width. We caution that because we do not have the molecular parameters needed for the S_1 term the comparison will only be for the spectroscopic effects (energies, wavefunctions, etc.) and not for effects of the vibrational dephasing

term. The transitions ranged from $J=8$ to 14 and were randomly selected. The comparison showed very small percent differences between the results for the two vibrational bands, generally between 0.01 and 0.02%. Note, it is the difference in energy from a state i to i' that enters the calculation and not the energy. Thus the spectroscopic part of the vibrational dependence is exceedingly small for the $\text{HNO}_3\text{-N}_2$ system.

Temperature dependence of the half-width

The temperature dependence of the half-width was determined for the 4979 ν_5 transitions studied in this work using the power law formula, Eq. (2). A “rule-of-thumb” expression for the temperature exponent has been given by Birnbaum [49]. For a “dipole-quadrupole” system, such as $\text{HNO}_3\text{-N}_2$, the “rule-of-thumb” temperature exponent is 0.833. Chu et al. [50] have studied the effect of changing the temperature exponent on retrieved mixing ratios of water vapor. They find that changing n from 0.5 to 0.7 results in roughly a 4% change in the mixing ratio at 10 km. It has also been demonstrated that temperature exponents averaged as a function of J or fit by polynomials in the rotational quantum numbers do not give reliable predictions for all transitions [51, 52]. Given the results of Chu et al. it is clear that the use of the specific measured or calculated temperature exponent for the ro-vibrational transition in question will yield the best results.

Some recent studies have shown that for certain types of radiator-perturber interactions the power law model is questionable. Wagner et al. [53] have observed that for certain transitions of water vapor perturbed by air, N_2 or O_2 the power law does not correctly model the temperature dependence of the half-width. This fact was also

demonstrated by Toth et al. [54] in a study of air-broadening of water vapor transitions in the region from 696-2163 cm⁻¹. In both studies it was found that the temperature exponent, n , can be negative for many transitions. In such cases the power law model, Eq. (2), is not valid. The mechanism leading to negative temperature exponents is called the resonance overtaking effect and was discussed by Wagner et al. [53], Antony et al. [55] and Hartmann et al. [56]. Thus, in this work the applicability of the power law model was tested.

Figure 3 shows the results of the least-squares fit to the data, straight line, to determine n . Plotted are $\ln[\gamma(T)/\gamma(T_0)]$ versus $\ln[T_0/T]$, where the top panel is for the $2_{11} \leftarrow 3_{12}$ transition and the bottom panel is for the $43_{431} \leftarrow 43_{430}$ transition. Both panels show that the fit line does not pass through all the points, indicating a better approximation for the temperature dependence may be needed, such as a double power law model [57]. However, for the transitions studied here the power law gives a reasonable description of the temperature dependence of the N₂-broadened half-width over the range T=200-500 K, suggesting the major contributions to the half-widths are from the $Re(S_2)$ terms [55].

Figure 4 shows the temperature exponent for N₂-broadening of HNO₃ versus $J''+0.9*(K_c''/J'')$ for the 4979 transitions studied here. The solid line at 0.833 is the “rule-of-thumb” value. The n values do not show large variation and range about $\pm 10\%$ about the “rule-of-thumb” value. There appears to be structure in the figure but with so many transitions it is difficult to obtain insight of how the temperature exponent might depend on the quantum numbers.

In Fig. 5 the temperature exponent is plotted versus $J''+0.9*(K_c''/J'')$ for the P-branch (top panel), Q-branch (middle panel), and R-branch (bottom panel) for only the $|\Delta K_c|=1$ transitions. The plot symbols used in the graph are K_c'' of the transition. The straight line is the “rule-of-thumb” value. For this subset of transitions, patterns can be seen. The temperature exponent for a given K_c'' changes smoothly as a function of $J''+0.9*(K_c''/J'')$. For J'' less than ~ 20 , at a fixed J'' n is largest for $K_c''=J''$ and decreases as K_c'' decreases. After $J''\sim 20$ the situation is reversed and n decreases as K_c'' increases. For other choices of $|\Delta K_c|$ the patterns are not as clear.

Comparison with measurements

There have been a number of measurements of N₂-broadening of HNO₃ [48, 58-61] and air-broadening of HNO₃ [62]. These data amount to 36 N₂-broadened and 7 air-broadened transitions with J' ranging from 10 to 44. These data along with the corresponding CRB calculated value are given in Table 4 ordered by J'' in the list. Figure 6 shows the N₂-broadened measurements with 2-sigma error bars (solid triangle symbols, ▲) and the CRB calculated values (⊕ symbols) versus the line number. The average percent difference between measurement and calculations is -2.5% with a standard deviation of 5.8%. One of the measured data (line 16) is much lower than the other measured data at similar J'' values or the calculated data. If this point is removed the average percent difference drops to -1.9. A number of the groups made measurements of nitrogen- and oxygen-broadening of HNO₃ transitions [48, 58-61] allowing the air-broadening value to be determined. The ratio of air to nitrogen broadening can then be taken for the 33 data points. This procedure yields an average ratio of 0.936 with a

minimum value of 0.897 and a max value of 0.961. Comparing the 7 air-broadened measurements of Cazzoli *et al.* to the N₂-broadened CRB calculations scaled by 0.936 gives an average percent difference of -0.17 and a standard deviation of 2.1.

5.0 Conclusions

Complex Robert-Bonamy calculations of the nitrogen-broadened half-widths for 4979 transitions of the ν_5 band of HNO₃ have been made at seven temperatures from 200 to 500 K. From these data the temperature dependence of the half-width has been determined for each transition. The results show that the power law model of the temperature dependence of the half-width works well for this collision system. Comparison of the calculated N₂-broadened half-widths and calculated N₂-broadened half-widths scaled to air-broadening with the measured values show very good agreement.

The half-widths determined in this work were scaled to air-broadening by multiplying them by 0.935 and used in simulations [22]. While improved agreement with measured spectra was observed (see Ref. [22] for details), scaling can introduce error on the order of $\pm 4\%$. Calculations of O₂-broadened half-widths for the 4979 transitions of the ν_5 band of HNO₃ studied in this work would eliminate this error. These calculations will be pursued in the future.

HNO₃ has 9 vibrational states. The first seven ones ($\nu_1 - \nu_7$) are of A' symmetry, while ν_8 and ν_9 are of A'' symmetry. For this reason, the observed vibrational-rotational

transitions are for the following selections rules for transitions between vibrational states $v' = |v_1, \dots, v_7, v_8, v_9\rangle$ and $v'' = |v_1, \dots, v_7, v_8, v_9\rangle$: For $\Delta|v_8+v_9| = \text{even}$ A-type and B-type transitions are observed ($\Delta|K_a| = \text{even}$, $\Delta|K_c| = \text{odd}$) and ($\Delta|K_a| = \text{odd}$, $\Delta|K_c| = \text{odd}$), respectively. This is the case for the ν_5 band, the ν_6 band and the $2\nu_9$ band and also for the $\nu_5+\nu_9-\nu_9$ hot band. Because little vibrational dependence was found for the half-widths for the $\text{HNO}_3\text{-N}_2$ collision system the calculations presented here can be used for these cases.

The N_2 -broadened half-widths and temperature dependence of the half-width determined in this work are available at the web site of one of the authors (faculty.uml.edu/Robert_Gamache) and the air-broadened half-width and temperature and exponent are in the supplementary data of Ref. [22].

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References

- [1] Solomon S. Stratospheric Ozone Depletion: A Review of Concepts and History, *Rev. Geophys.* 1999; **37**: 275–316.
- [2] Santee ML, Manney GL, Froidevaux L, Read WG, Waters JW. Six years of UARS Microwave Limb Sounder HNO₃ observations: Seasonal, interhemispheric, and interannual variations in the lower stratosphere, *J. Geophys. Res.* 1999; **104**: 8225–46.
- [3] Santee ML, Manney GL, Livesey NJ, Read WG. Threedimensional structure and evolution of stratospheric HNO₃ based on UARS Microwave Limb Sounder measurements, *J. Geophys. Res.* 2004; **109**: D15306.
- [4] Crutzen PJ. Ozone production rates in oxygen-hydrogen-nitrogen oxide atmosphere, *J. Geophys. Res.* 1971; **78**: 7311.
- [5] Johnston HS. Reduction of stratospheric ozone by nitrogen oxide catalysts from supersonic transport exhaust, *Science* 1971; **173**: 517-22.
- [6] Coffey MT, Hannigan JW, Goldman A, Kinnison D, Gille JC, Barnett JJ, Froidevaux L, Lambert A, Santee M, Livesey N, Fisher B, Kulawik SS, Beer R. Airborne Fourier transform spectrometer observations in support of EOS Aura validation, *J. Geophys. Res.* 2008; **113**: D16S42.
- [7] Waters JW, Froidevaux L, Harwood RS, Jarnot RF, Pickett HM, Read WG, Siegel PH, Cofield RE, Filipiak MJ, Flower DA, Holden JR, Lau GK, Livesey NJ, Manney GL, Pumphrey HC, Santee ML, Wu DL, Cuddy DT, Lay RR, Loo MS, Perun VS, Schwartz MJ, Stek PC, Thurstans RP, Boyles MA, Chandra KM, Chavez MC, Chen G-S, Chudasama BV, Dodge R, Fuller RA, Girard MA, Jiang JH, Jiang Y, Knosp BW, Remi C, LaBelle, Lam JC, Lee KA, Miller D, Oswald JE, Patel NC, Pukala DM, Quintero O, Scaff DM, Snyder WV, Tope MC, Wagner PA, Walch MJ. The Earth Observing System Microwave Limb Sounder (EOS MLS) on the Aura Satellite, *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON GEOSCIENCE AND REMOTE SENSING* 2006; **44**: 1075-92.
- [8] Gille J, Barnett J, Arter P, Barker M, Bernath P, Boone C, Cavanaugh C, Chow J, Coffey M, Craft J, Craig C, Dials M, Dean V, Eden T, Edwards DP, Francis G, Halvorson C, Harvey L, Hepplewhite C, Khosravi R, Kinnison D, Krinsky C, Lambert A, Lee H, Lyjak L, Loh J, Mankin W, Massie S, McInerney J, Moorhouse J, Nardi B, Packman D, Randall C, Reburn J, Rudolf W, Schwartz M, Serafin J, Stone K, Torpy B, Walker K, Waterfall A, Watkins R, Whitney J, Woodard D, Young G. High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder: Experiment overview, recovery, and validation of initial temperature data, 113,, , 2008; **113**: D16S43.
- [9] Beer R. TES on the Aura Mission: Scientific Objectives, Measurements, and Analysis Overview, *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON GEOSCIENCE AND REMOTE SENSING*, VOL. 44, NO. 5, 2006; **44**: 1102-5.
- [10] Kinnison DE, Gille JC, Barnett JJ, Randall CE, Harvey VL, Lambert A, Khosravi R, Alexander MJ, Bernath PF, Boone CD, Cavanaugh C, Coffey MT, Craig C, Dean V, Eden T, Ellis D, Fahey DW, Francis G, Halvorson C, Hannigan JW, Hartsough C, Hepplewhite C, Krinsky C, Lee H, Mankin WG, Marcy T, Massie ST, Nardi B, Packman D, Popp PJ, Santee ML, Yudin V, Walker KA, Global

- Observations of HNO₃ from the High Resolution Dynamics Limb Sounder (HIRDLS) - First results. 2008.
- [11] Santee ML, Lambert A, Read WG, Livesey NJ, Cofield RE, Cuddy DT, Daffer WH, Drouin BJ, Froidevaux L, Fuller RA, Jarnot RF, Knosp BW, Manney GL, Perun VS, Snyder WV, Stek PC, Thurstans RP, Wagner PA, Waters JW, Muscari G, Zafra RLd, Dibb JE, Fahey DW, Popp PJ, Marcy TP, Jucks KW, Toon GC, Stachnik RA, Bernath PF, Boone CD, Walker KA, Urban J, Murtagh D. Validation of the Aura Microwave Limb Sounder HNO₃ measurements, *J. geophys. Res.* 2007; **112**: D24S40.
- [12] Toon GC. The JPL MkIV interferometer, *Opt. Photon, News* 1991; **2**: 19– 21.
- [13] Jucks KW, Johnson DG, Chance KV, Traub WA, Salawitch RJ. Nitric acid in the middle stratosphere as a function of altitude and aerosol loading, *J. Geophys. Res.* 1999; **104**: 26,715– 26,23.
- [14] Stachnik RA, Salawitch R, Engel A, Schmidt U. Measurements of chlorine partitioning in the winter Arctic stratosphere, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 1999; **26**: 3093–6.
- [15] Scheuer E, Talbot RW, Dibb JE, Seid GK, DeBell L, Lefer B. Seasonal distributions of fine aerosol sulfate in the North American Arctic basin during TOPSE, *J. Geophys. Res.* 2003; **108**.
- [16] Neumen JA, Gao RS, Fahey DW, Holecek JC, Ridley BA, Walega JG, Grahek FE, Richard EC, McElroy CT, Thompson TL, Elkins JW, Moore FL, Ray EA. In situ measurements of HNO₃, NO_y, NO, and O₃ in the lower stratosphere and upper troposphere, *Atmos. Environ.* 2001; **35**: 5789–97.
- [17] Fischer H, Oelhaf H. Remote sensing of vertical profiles of atmospheric trace constituents with MIPAS limb-emission spectrometers, *Appl. Opt.* 1996; **35**: 2787– 96.
- [18] Fischer H, Birk M, Blom C, Carli B, Carlotti M, von Clarmann T, Delbouille L, Dudhia A, Ehhalt D, Endemann M, Flaud JM, Gessner R, Kleinert A, Koopmann R, Langen J, Lopez-Puertas M, Mosner P, Nett H, Oelhaf H, Perron G, Remedios J, Ridolfi M, Stiller G, Zander R. MIPAS: an instrument for atmospheric and climate research, *Atmos. Chem. Phys. Discuss.* 2007; **7**: 8795-893.
- [19] Murtagh D, Frisk U, Merino F, Ridal M, Jonsson A, Stegman J, Witt G, Eriksson P, Jiménez C, Megie G, de la Noë J, Ricaud P, Baron P, Pardo JR, Hauchcorne A, Llewellyn EJ, Degenstein DA, Gattinger RL, Lloyd ND, Evans WF, McDade IC, Haley CS, Sioris C, Savigny Cv, Solheim BH, McConnell JC, Strong K, Richardson EH, Leppelmeier GW, Kyrölä E, Auvinen H, Oikarinen L. An overview of the Odin atmospheric mission, *Can J. Phys.* 2002; **80**: 309– 19.
- [20] Irie H, Kondo Y, Koike M, Danilin MY, Camy-Peyret C, Payan S, Pommereau JP, Goutail F, Oelhaf H, Wetzels G, Toon GC, Sen B, Bevilacqua RM, III JMR, Renard JB, Kanzawa H, Nakajima H, Yokota T, Sugita T, Sasano Y. Validation of NO₂ and HNO₃ measurements from the Improved Limb Atmospheric Spectrometer (ILAS) with the version 5.20 retrieval algorithm, *J. Geophys. Res.* 2002; **107**: 8206.
- [21] Bernath PF, McElroy CT, Abrams MC, Boone CD, Butler M, Camy-Peyret C, Carleer M, Clerbaux C, Coheur P-F, Colin R, DeCola P, DeMazière M, Drummond JR, Dufour D, Evans WFJ, Fast H, Fussen D, Gilbert K, Jennings DE,

- Llewellyn EJ, Lowe RP, Mahieu E, McConnell JC, McHugh M, McLeod SD, Michaud R, Midwinter C, Nassar R, Nichitiu F, Nowlan C, Rinsland CP, Rochon YJ, Rowlands N, Semeniuk K, Simon P, Skelton R, Sloan JJ, Soucy M-A, Strong K, Tremblay P, Turnbull D, Walker KA, Walkty I, Wardle DA, Wehrle V, Zander R, Zou J. Atmospheric Chemistry Experiment (ACE): Mission overview, *Geophys. Res. Lett.* 2005; **32**: L15S01.
- [22] Gomez L, Tran H, Perrin A, Gamache RR, Laraia A, Orphal J, Chelin P, Fellows CE, Hartmann J-M, Some improvements of the HNO₃ spectroscopic parameters in the spectral region from 600 to 950 cm⁻¹, in in press, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer.* 2008.
- [23] Rothman LS, Jacquemart D, Barbe A, Benner DC, Birk M, Brown LR, Carleer MR, Chackerian C, Jr., Chance K, Coudert LH, Dana V, Devi VM, Flaud J-M, Gamache RR, Goldman A, Hartmann J-M, Jucks KW, Maki AG, Mandin J-Y, Massie ST, Orphal J, Perrin A, Rinsland CP, Smith MAH, Tennyson J, Tolchenov RN, Toth RA, Vander Auwera J, Varanasi P, Wagner G. The HITRAN 2004 Molecular Spectroscopic Database, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 2005; **96**: 139-204.
- [24] Jacquinet-Husson N, Arie' E, Ballard J, Barbe A, Bjoraker G, Bonnet B, Brown LR, Camy-Peyret C, Champion J-P, Che'din A, Chursin A, Clerbaux C, Duxbury G, Flaud J-M, Fourrie' N, Fayt A, Graner G, Gamache RR, Goldman A, Golovko V, Guelachvili G, Hartmann J-M, Hilico JC, Hillman J, Lefe`vre G, Lellouch E, Mikhailenko SN, Naumenko OV, Nemtchinov V, Newnham DA, Nikitin A, Orphal J, Perrin A, Reuter DC, Rinsland CP, Rosenmann L, Rothman LS, Scott NA, Selby J, Sinitza LN, Sirota JM, Smith MAH, Smith KM, Tyuterev VG, Tipping RH, Urban S, Varanasi P, Weber M. The 1997 spectroscopic GEISA databank, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 1999; **62**: 205-54.
- [25] Flaud J-M, Brizzi G, Carlotti M, Perrin A, Ridolfi M. MIPAS database: Validation of HNO₃ line parameters using MIPAS satellite measurements., *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 2006; **6**: 5037-48.
- [26] Perrin A, Flaud J-M, Keller F, Goldman A, Blatherwick RD, Murcay FJ, Rinsland CP. Analysis of the $\nu_8+\nu_9$ band of HNO₃: line positions and intensities, and resonances involving the $\nu_6=\nu_7=1$ dark state, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 1999; **194**: 113– 23.
- [27] Perrin A, Orphal J, Flaud J-M, Klee S, Mellau G, Mäder H, Walbrodt D, Winnewisser M. New analysis of the ν_5 and $2\nu_9$ bands of HNO₃ by infrared and millimeter wave techniques: line positions and intensities, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 2004; **228**: 375–91.
- [28] Chackerian C, Sharpe SW, Blake TA. Anhydrous nitric acid integrated absorption cross sections: 820-5300 cm⁻¹, *J. Quant. Spectros. Radiat. Transfer* 2003; **82**: 429-41.
- [29] Perrin A, Puzzarini C, Colmont J-M, Verdes C, Wlodarczak G, Cazzoli G, Buehler S, Flaud J-M, Demaison J. Molecular Line Parameters for the "MASTER" (Millimeter Wave Acquisitions for Stratosphere/Troposphere Exchange Research) Database, *Atmos. Chem.* 2005; **51**: 161–205.
- [30] Perrin A. Recent progress in the analysis of HNO₃ spectra, *Spectrochimica Acta Part A* 1998; **54**: 375-93.

- [31] Robert D, Bonamy J. Short range force effects in semiclassical molecular line broadening calculations, *Journal De Physique* 1979; **20**: 923-43.
- [32] Lynch R. Half-widths and line shifts of water vapor perturbed by both nitrogen and oxygen. Ph.D. dissertation, University of Massachusetts Lowell, June, 1995.
- [33] R. R. Gamache RL, and S. P. Neshyba. New Developments in the Theory of Pressure-Broadening and Pressure-Shifting of Spectral Lines of H₂O: The Complex Robert-Bonamy Formalism, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 1998; **59**: 319-35.
- [34] R. Lynch RRG, and S. P. Neshyba. N₂ and O₂ Induced Halfwidths and Line Shifts of Water Vapor Transitions in the (301) \leftarrow (000) and (221) \leftarrow (000) Bands, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 1998; **59**: 595-613.
- [35] Baranger M. General impact theory of pressure broadening, *Phys Rev* 1958; **112**: 855-65.
- [36] Ben-Reuven A, *Spectral Line Shapes in Gases in the Binary-Collision Approximation*, *Adv. Chem. Phys.*, Prigogine I and Rice SA, Editors. 1975, Academic Press: New York. p. 235.
- [37] Hirschfelder JO, Curtiss CF, Bird RB. *Molecular Theory of Gases and Liquids*, Wiley, New York 1964.
- [38] Sack RA. Two-Center Expansion for the Powers of the Distance Between Two Points, *J. Math. Phys.* 1964; **5**: 260-8.
- [39] Neshyba SP, Gamache RR. Improved Line Broadening Coefficients for Asymmetric Rotor Molecules: Application to Ozone Perturbed by Nitrogen, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. and Radiat. Transfer* 1993; **50**: 443-53.
- [40] Watson JKG. Determination of centrifugal Distortion Coefficients of Asymmetric- Top Molecules, *J. Chem. Phys.* 1967; **46**: 1935-49.
- [41] Goldman A, Burkholder JB, Howard CJ, Escribano R, Maki AG. Spectroscopic Constants for the ν_9 Infrared Band of HNO₃, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 1988; **131**: 195-200.
- [42] Maki AG, Wells JS. Measurement and Analysis of the Fermi Resonance between ν_5 and $2\nu_9$ of Nitric Acid, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 1992; **152**: 69-79.
- [43] Huber KP, Herzberg G. *Molecular Spectra and Molecular Structure: Constants of Diatomic Molecules*, Van Nostrand, New York 1979.
- [44] Cox AP, Riveros JM. Microwave Spectrum and Structure of Nitric Acid, *J. Chem. Phys.* 1965; **42**: 3106-12.
- [45] Mulder F, van Dijk G, van der Avoird A. Multipole moments, polarizabilities and anisotropic long range interaction coefficients for N₂, *Mol. Phys.* 1980; **39**: 407-25.
- [46] Albinus L, Spieckermann J, Sutter DH. The Electric Field Gradient Tensor and the Tensors of the Molecular Magnetic Susceptibility and the Molecular Electric Quadrupole Moment in Nitric Acid: A High-Resolution Rotational Zeeman Effect Study, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 1989; **133**: 128-47.
- [47] Bouanich J-P. Site-Site Lennard- Jones Potential Parameters for N₂, O₂, H₂, CO and CO₂, *J. Quant Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 1992; **47**: 243-50.
- [48] Goyette TM, Cohen EA, DeLucia FC. Pressure Broadening of HNO₃ by N₂ and O₂: An Intercomparison of Results in the Millimeter Wave Region, *J. Quant. Spectros. Radiat. Transfer* 1998; **60**: 77-84.

- [49] Birnbaum G. Microwave Pressure Broadening and its Application to Intermolecular Forces, *Advances in Chem. Phys.* 1967; **12**: 487-548.
- [50] Chu WP, Chiou EW, Larsen JC, Thomason LW, Rind D, Buglia JJ, Oltmans S, McCormick MP, McMaster LM. Algorithms and Sensitivity Analyses for Stratospheric Aerosol and Gas Experiment II Water Vapor Retrieval, *J. Geophys. Res.* 1993; **98**: 4857-66.
- [51] Gamache RR, Neshyba SP, Plateaux JJ, Barbe A, Régalia L, Pollack JB. CO₂-Broadening of Water-Vapor Lines, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 1995; **170**: 131-51.
- [52] Gamache RR, Lynch R, Brown LR. Theoretical Calculations of Pressure Broadening Coefficients for H₂O Perturbed by Hydrogen or Helium Gas, *J. Quant. Spectros. Radiat. Transfer* 1996; **56**: 471-87.
- [53] Wagner G, Birk M, Gamache RR, Hartmann J-M. Collisional parameters of H₂O lines: effects of temperature, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 2005; **92**: 211-30.
- [54] Toth RA, Brown LR, Smith MAH, Malathy Devi V, Chris Benner D, Dulick M. Air-broadening of H₂O as a function of temperature: 696-2163 cm⁻¹, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 2006; **101**: 339-66.
- [55] Antony BK, Neshyba S, Gamache RR. Self-broadening of water vapor transitions via the complex Robert-Bonamy theory, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 2006; **105**: 148-63.
- [56] Hartmann JM, Taine J, Bonamy J, Labani B, Robert D. Collisional broadening of rotation-vibration lines for asymmetric-top molecules II. H₂O diode laser measurements in the 400-900 K range; calculations in the 300-2000 K range, *J. Chem. Phys.* 1987; **86**: 144-56.
- [57] Gamache RR. Analytical evaluation of the Maxwell-Boltzmann velocity average in pressure-broadened half-width calculations, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 2001; **208**: 79-86.
- [58] Zu L, Hamilton PA, Davies PB. Pressure broadening and frequency measurements of nitric acid lines in the 683 GHz region, *J. Quant. Spectros. Radiat. Transfer* **2002**; **73**: 545-56.
- [59] Goyette TM, Ebenstein WL, Lucia FCD, Helminger P. Pressure Broadening of the Millimeter and Submillimeter Wave Spectra of Nitric Acid by Oxygen and Nitrogen, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 1988; **128**: 108-16.
- [60] Goyette TM, Guo W, Delucia FC, Helminger P. Variable Temperature Pressure Broadening of HNO₃ in the Millimeter Wave Spectral Region, *J. Quant. Spectrosc. Radiat. Transfer* 1991; **46**: 293-7.
- [61] Colmont J-M, Bakri B, Rohart Fo, Wlodarczak G. Experimental determination of pressure-broadening parameters of millimeter-wave transitions of HNO₃ perturbed by N₂ and O₂, and of their temperature dependences, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 2003; **220**: 52-7.
- [62] Cazzoli G, Dore L, Puzzarini C, Bakri B, Colmont J-M, Rohart F, Wlodarczak G. Experimental determination of air-broadening parameters of pure rotational transitions of HNO₃: intercomparison of measurements by using different techniques, *J. Mol. Spectrosc.* 2005; **229**: 158-69.

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- 4 Measured N₂- and air-broadened half-widths and the corresponding CRB calculated value.

Table 1. Values of the heteronuclear atom-atom parameters for the HNO₃-N₂ collision pair.

Atomic pair	σ /Angstrom	ϵ/k_B (K)
H-N	2.99	20.45
N-N	3.29	37.16
O-N	3.15	43.88

Table 2. Adjustment of the trajectory parameters to match eight measurements of Goyette *et al.* [48].

Trajectory parameters		$\varepsilon/k_B(K)=145.25$ $\sigma/A=4.170$	$\varepsilon/k_B(K)=165.00$ $\sigma/A=3.117$
Transition	Exp	cal _{initial}	cal _{final}
$16_{016} \leftarrow 15_{015}$	0.11966	0.13299	0.12641
$14_{212} \leftarrow 13_{211}$	0.12676	0.13493	0.12832
$13_{310} \leftarrow 12_{39}^*$	0.13385	0.13346	0.12697
$12_{58} \leftarrow 11_{57}$	0.12650	0.13564	0.12899
$11_{66} \leftarrow 10_{65}$	0.13335	0.13556	0.12885
$24_{816} \leftarrow 24_{817}$	0.11053	0.12590	0.11702
$25_{916} \leftarrow 25_{917}^*$	0.11915	0.12394	0.11479
$26_{1016} \leftarrow 26_{1017}^*$	0.11433	0.12368	0.11427

* 300 K

Table 3 Calculated half-widths and their temperature dependence for the sequence of transitions with *index* running from 1297 ($36_{0\ 36}$) to 1397 ($36_{36\ 0}$). In the K_a columns (resp. K_c columns), the letter “d” stands for degenerate K_a values, with $K_a=J-K_c$ and $K_a=J-K_c+1$ (resp. for degenerate K_c values with $K_c=J-K_a$ and $K_c=J-K_a+1$).

Upper state	Lower state	γ cm ⁻¹ atm ⁻¹	<i>n</i>
36 _{36 d}	36 _{36 d}	96.89	0.915(0.171)
36 _{35 d}	36 _{35 d}	100.68	0.915(0.156)
36 _{34 d}	36 _{34 d}	104.54	0.916(0.143)
37 _{d 34}	36 _{d 33}	104.79	0.763(0.077)
37 _{d 35}	36 _{d 34}	104.81	0.759(0.073)
37 _{d 33}	36 _{d 32}	104.82	0.766(0.080)
37 _{d 36}	36 _{d 35}	104.89	0.756(0.069)
37 _{d 32}	36 _{d 31}	104.93	0.769(0.082)
37 _{d 37}	36 _{d 36}	105.05	0.753(0.064)
37 _{d 31}	36 _{d 30}	105.12	0.773(0.084)
35 _{2 33}	36 _{2 34}	105.38	0.757(0.069)
37 _{d 30}	36 _{d 29}	105.39	0.778(0.086)
35 _{d 34}	36 _{d 35}	105.41	0.753(0.065)
35 _{d 32}	36 _{d 33}	105.41	0.761(0.073)
35 _{d 31}	36 _{d 32}	105.51	0.765(0.077)
35 _{d 35}	36 _{d 36}	105.64	0.751(0.060)
35 _{d 30}	36 _{d 31}	105.66	0.768(0.079)
37 _{d 29}	36 _{d 28}	105.72	0.783(0.088)
35 _{d 29}	36 _{d 30}	105.86	0.772(0.081)
37 _{d 28}	36 _{d 27}	106.10	0.789(0.090)
35 _{d 28}	36 _{d 29}	106.12	0.777(0.083)
35 _{d 27}	36 _{d 28}	106.46	0.782(0.084)
37 _{d 27}	36 _{d 26}	106.55	0.794(0.091)
35 _{d 26}	36 _{d 27}	106.85	0.787(0.086)
37 _{d 26}	36 _{d 25}	107.10	0.800(0.091)
35 _{d 25}	36 _{d 26}	107.28	0.793(0.087)
37 _{d 25}	36 _{d 24}	107.70	0.805(0.091)
35 _{d 24}	36 _{d 25}	107.78	0.798(0.088)
37 _{d 24}	36 _{d 23}	108.35	0.813(0.092)
35 _{d 23}	36 _{d 24}	108.38	0.806(0.089)
37 _{d 23}	36 _{d 22}	109.08	0.822(0.093)
35 _{d 22}	36 _{d 23}	109.09	0.815(0.091)
36 _{32 d}	36 _{33 d}	109.50	0.920(0.129)

35 _{d 21}	36 _{d 22}	109.87	0.825(0.093)
37 _{d 22}	36 _{d 21}	109.87	0.832(0.095)
35 _{d 20}	36 _{d 21}	110.67	0.835(0.094)
37 _{d 21}	36 _{d 20}	110.70	0.842(0.097)
35 _{d 19}	36 _{d 20}	111.51	0.845(0.096)
37 _{d 20}	36 _{d 19}	111.55	0.852(0.099)
36 _{33 4}	36 _{30 7}	112.40	0.922(0.120)
37 _{18 19}	36 _{18 18}	112.42	0.863(0.100)
37 _{19 19}	36 _{19 18}	112.42	0.863(0.100)
36 _{33 3}	36 _{30 6}	112.50	0.922(0.120)
35 _{19 17}	36 _{18 18}	113.30	0.867(0.100)
37 _{19 18}	36 _{20 17}	113.30	0.872(0.101)
36 _{30 7}	36 _{32 4}	113.59	0.922(0.116)
35 _{20 15}	36 _{19 18}	114.30	0.878(0.101)
36 _{29 8}	36 _{32 5}	114.76	0.923(0.113)
37 _{23 15}	36 _{22 14}	116.13	0.901(0.102)
37 _{22 15}	36 _{23 14}	116.13	0.901(0.102)
36 _{26 10}	36 _{31 5}	117.12	0.924(0.105)
37 _{24 14}	36 _{25 11}	117.83	0.914(0.100)
36 _{27 9}	36 _{31 6}	118.11	0.927(0.103)
37 _{25 12}	36 _{26 11}	118.62	0.921(0.100)
37 _{27 11}	36 _{27 10}	118.90	0.924(0.099)
37 _{26 11}	36 _{26 10}	119.52	0.925(0.097)
37 _{29 8}	36 _{29 7}	119.58	0.930(0.097)
37 _{26 12}	36 _{27 9}	120.04	0.927(0.096)
37 _{28 9}	36 _{28 8}	121.04	0.933(0.091)

Table 4 Measured N₂- and air-broadened half-widths and the corresponding CRB calculated value.

Line	perturber	J' Ka' Kc'	J'' Ka'' Kc''	γ_{Exp}^{\dagger}	Ref	γ_{CRB}^{\dagger}
1	N ₂	11 _{6 6}	10 _{6 5}	0.11712	[59]	0.12848
2	N ₂	11 _{9 3}	10 _{9 2}	0.13297	[48]	0.12546
3	N ₂	12 _{6 6}	11 _{6 5}	0.13436	[59]	0.12724
4	N ₂	12 _{5 8}	11 _{5 7}	0.12673	[48]	0.12863
5	N ₂	13 _{11 2}	12 _{11 1}	0.12346	[59]	0.12329
6	N ₂	13 _{3 10}	12 _{3 9}	0.13298	[48]	0.12846
7	N ₂	14 _{8 6}	13 _{8 5}	0.12371	[59]	0.12503
8	N ₂	14 _{2 12}	13 _{2 11}	0.13350	[61]	0.12797
8	N ₂	14 _{2 12}	13 _{2 11}	0.12977	[48]	0.12797
9	N ₂	14 _{4 10}	13 _{4 9}	0.12574	[59]	0.12712
10	N ₂	14 _{3 12}	14 _{3 11}	0.13282	[61]	0.12736
11	air	15 _{13 3}	14 _{13 2}	0.11595	[62]	0.11231*
12	N ₂	16 _{0 16}	15 _{0 15}	0.12179	[48]	0.12607
13	N ₂	18 _{0 18}	17 _{0 17}	0.11585	[59]	0.12386
13	N ₂	18 _{0 18}	17 _{0 17}	0.12040	[60]	0.12386
14	N ₂	18 _{12 7}	17 _{12 6}	0.12092	[59]	0.12244
15	N ₂	19 _{3 16}	18 _{3 15}	0.11636	[59]	0.12174
16	N ₂	20 _{15 5}	19 _{15 4}	0.09887	[59]	0.12277
17	N ₂	22 _{7 15}	21 _{7 14}	0.11712	[59]	0.11929
17	N ₂	22 _{7 15}	21 _{7 14}	0.11547	[60]	0.11929
18	N ₂	22 _{0 22}	21 _{0 21}	0.10622	[59]	0.11899
19	N ₂	24 _{13 11}	23 _{14 10}	0.11407	[61]	0.11971
20	N ₂	24 _{8 16}	24 _{8 17}	0.11518	[48]	0.11670
21	air	25 _{0 25}	24 _{0 24}	0.10627	[62]	0.10847*
22	N ₂	25 _{9 16}	25 _{9 17}	0.11904	[48]	0.11558
23	N ₂	26 _{9 17}	25 _{9 16}	0.11154	[59]	0.11564
24	N ₂	26 _{10 16}	26 _{10 17}	0.11514	[48]	0.11545
25	air	26 _{1 25}	26 _{0 26}	0.10675	[62]	0.10719*
26	air	27 _{0 27}	26 _{0 26}	0.10517	[62]	0.10695*
27	N ₂	27 _{9 18}	26 _{9 17}	0.10825	[59]	0.11459
28	air	27 _{2 25}	27 _{1 26}	0.10855	[62]	0.10601*
29	N ₂	29 _{0 29}	28 _{0 28}	0.10743	[60]	0.11250
29	N ₂	29 _{0 29}	28 _{0 28}	0.10216	[59]	0.11250
30	N ₂	30 _{14 16}	30 _{14 17}	0.11410	[58]	0.11450
31	N ₂	31 _{22 9}	30 _{22 8}	0.11260	[58]	0.12046
32	N ₂	32 _{23 10}	31 _{23 9}	0.11330	[58]	0.11907
33	N ₂	32 _{28 5}	31 _{28 4}	0.11990	[58]	0.11125
34	N ₂	32 _{28 4}	31 _{28 3}	0.10570	[58]	0.11126
35	N ₂	35 _{0 35}	34 _{0 34}	0.10343	[59]	0.10646
35	N ₂	35 _{0 35}	34 _{0 34}	0.10340	[58]	0.10646
36	N ₂	36 _{0 36}	35 _{0 35}	0.10673	[59]	0.10562

36	N ₂	36 _{0 36}	35 _{0 35}	0.10670	[58]	0.10562
37	N ₂	38 _{5 33}	37 _{5 32}	0.10545	[61]	0.10421
38	air	43 _{18 25}	43 _{17 26}	0.09684	[62]	0.09984*
39	air	44 _{19 25}	44 _{18 26}	0.09714	[62]	0.09983*

† in units of cm⁻¹ atm⁻¹, * scaled to air-broadening by 0.936*γ(N₂)

List of Figures

Figure

- 1 Calculated N₂-broadened half-widths of ν_5 transitions of HNO₃ versus $J''+0.9*(K_c''/J'')$. The plot symbols are K_c'' .
- 2 Top panel: Calculated N₂-broadened half-widths for transitions with $J''=27$ versus the rotational state *index*, $(J''*(J''+1)+K_a''-K_c''+1)$, plotted are the data for *index* running from 730 (27_{027}) to 784 (27_{270}). The symbols are an asterisk (*) for the P-branch, open circle (O) for the Q-branch, and open delta (Δ) for the R-branch transitions. Bottom panel: Same as above with plot symbols equal to K_c'' .
- 3 $\ln[\gamma(T)/\gamma(T_0)]$ versus $\ln[T_0/T]$; data are for N₂-broadening of ν_5 transitions, the top panel is for the $2_{11} \leftarrow 3_{12}$ transition and the bottom panel is for the $43_{431} \leftarrow 43_{430}$ transition.
- 4 Temperature exponents for N₂-broadening of 4979 ν_5 transitions of HNO₃ versus $J''+0.9*(K_c''/J'')$. Solid horizontal line is the dipole-quadrupole “rule-of-thumb” value, 0.833.
- 5 Temperature exponent versus $J''+0.9*(K_c''/J'')$ for the P-branch (top panel), Q-branch (middle panel), and R-branch (bottom panel) for the $|\Delta K_c|=1$ transitions. The plot symbols are K_c'' . Solid horizontal line is the dipole-quadrupole “rule-of-thumb” value, 0.833.

- 6 Measured N₂-broadening half-widths with 2 sigma error bars (triangle symbol, ▲), the corresponding CRB calculated value (⊕ symbol) versus the line count.

Figure(s)

Figure(s)

$\text{HNO}_3\text{-N}_2$ measurement vs. calculation